

ThrombUS+ Study A Annotation Manual

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
ACEP	American College of Emergency Physicians

Executive Summary

ThrombUS+ Study A aims to collect and create a labelled ultrasound image data set containing ultrasound image series and video clips of patients that undergo routine ultrasound scans on lower limbs, because of suspected deep vein thrombosis. The data will be used to train an AI model within ThrombUS+ project to achieve automated detection of deep vein thrombosis on conventional ultrasound scans. This document describes in detail the steps required to annotate the acquired image series and videos using the V7 labs Darwin annotation platform.

1. Introduction

This document (manual) outlines the step-by-step procedure for accessing and annotating data on the V7 labs Darwin annotation platform, that will be used for the development of the AI models for the ThrombUS+ project.

1.1. Labelling of Vascular Structures

1. **Goal:** Accurate identification and labelling of anatomical structures and potential pathologies.
2. **Label:** Segmentation mask (anatomical structures tracing) for the following categories:
 - **Target Veins:** Key focus for DVT diagnosis:
 - Common Femoral Vein (CFV)
 - Great Saphenous Vein (GSV)
 - Femoral Vein (FV)
 - Popliteal Vein (PV)
 - **Accompanying Arteries:** Helps distinguish arteries from veins and supports pressure assessments:
 - Common Femoral Artery (CFA)
 - Deep Femoral Artery (DFA)
 - Femoral Artery (FA)
 - Popliteal Artery (PA)
 - **Clots:** Thrombi clots.
 - **Other:** Pathologies or structures that may be mischaracterized as DVT (other pathology class)

1.2. Ultrasound Image Grading of Target Veins

1. **Goal:** Evaluate ultrasound image quality to determine their suitability for diagnostic purposes.
2. **Label:** Classification Tag based on the American College of Emergency Physicians (ACEP) five-point grading scale Table 1.
 - **Scores 1-2:** Non diagnostic.
 - **Scores 3-5:** Diagnostic

Table 1. Diagnostic grading scales according to ACEP

Grading Scale	1	2	3	4	5
Grading scale definition	No recognizable structures, no objective data can be gathered	Minimally recognizable structures but insufficient for diagnosis	Minimal criteria met for diagnosis, recognizable structures but with some technical or other flaws	Minimal criteria met for diagnosis, all structures imaged well, and diagnosis easily supported	Minimal criteria met for diagnosis, all structures imaged with excellent image quality and diagnosis completely supported

2. Labelling Instructions

The following is a set of instructions for the annotation of the ultrasound images/videos during ThrombUS+ Clinical Study A. Frames must be annotated based on the diagnostic criteria used during a DVT exam to capture clinically relevant information.

- In a DICOM video on V7, please disregard the first four frames and **begin labelling from the fifth** frame onward.
- On average, **5 to 7 frames should be annotated per video** to balance data richness and labelling efficiency.
- For an inadequate DICOM image on V7, **apply the corresponding ACEP grading score and, if image quality permits (ACEP grade ≥ 2), segment (trace) all visible structures, including veins, arteries, and clots.**

The key frame selection criteria for the DICOM videos include:

1. Non-compressed/Neutral phase (1 frame):

- a) Frames where veins are of **their original shape and size** representing the neutral non-compressed state (Figure 1).
- b) In some cases, the video may begin in a partially compressed state. **If the neutral phase of the vessels appears later in the clip, after compression is released, please ensure it is still annotated.**

Figure 1. An example of annotating arteries and veins in the non-compressed/ neutral phase. Left: a single frame from a multi-frame DICOM file. Right: Annotation of CFV (blue) and CFA (red).

2. Mild-Compression Phase (2-3 frames):

- a) Frames where veins are **partially compressed** (Figure 2).
- b) A total of 2-3 frames should be labelled.
 - One frame should be selected a few frames after the neutral phase, where the vein has visibly decreased in size.

- Another should be chosen a few frames before the vein is fully compressed or collapsed, showing a significant reduction in size.
- If possible, an additional frame can be included between these two points.

Figure 2. An example of annotating arteries and veins in a partially compressed state. Left: a single frame from a multi-frame DICOM file. Right: Annotation of CFV (blue) and CFA (red).

3. Peak Compression Phase (1 frame):

- Frames where veins **either collapse or fail to collapse** under applied pressure should be labelled.
 - **For normal patients:** The vein will collapse completely, and this frame should be labelled. Even if the collapsed vein is difficult to distinguish, a very thin segmentation mask (tracing) should be applied where its border is best estimated.
 - **For pathological patients:** The vein will not fully compress, but a segmentation mask is still required at the frame where peak pressure is applied (usually when the accompanying artery is slightly deformed).

Figure 3. An example of annotating arteries and veins in a fully compressed state. Left: a single frame from a multi-frame DICOM file. Right: Annotation of CFV (blue) and CFA (red).

4. Artery Deformation (1-2 frames):

- In addition to the previously mentioned key frames, where all visible veins, arteries, and clots are labelled, please also annotate **1-2 frames capturing the deformation of the arterial walls**.
- This marks the point at which compression should be stopped, especially in pathological cases where the compression increases, and the vein fails to collapse.

Figure 4. An example of annotating deformed arteries. Left: a single frame from a multi-frame DICOM file. Right: Annotation of CFV (blue) and CFA (red).

3. Registration and Login

3.1. Creating a V7 Labs Darwin Account

You will receive an email invitation from Echonus to join the V7 annotation platform (Figure 5). This invitation will be sent to the same email address you use for ThrombUS-related tasks and meetings. The email includes a registration link to create your V7 annotator/worker account.

1. Click the "Join the Team" button in the email.
2. Enter your **first and last name**, set a **strong, unique password**, and complete your account setup (Figure 6).
3. Store your password securely and **do not share** it to maintain data confidentiality and security.

Once your account is set up, you can proceed with the annotation workflow detailed in the following sections.

Figure 5. The invitation email to join the annotation platform*.

Figure 6. The creation of password step.

*Please note that the link above expires after first use. To access your account after its creation, navigate to the V7 Darwin login page and enter your email address and password configured during the registration process.

4. Requesting and Accessing Data on V7

After logging into the annotation platform, you will see a dashboard displaying your hospital’s dataset. From here, follow these steps (Table 2):

Table 2. Steps to be followed for requesting access to images for annotation.

No. Step	Description	Image
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- 1 **Read the Instructions** – Click the "Read Instructions" button to review the annotation guidelines. This is the first and most crucial step to ensure consistency in the labelling process.

- 2 **Request Data** – Once you have read and understood the instructions, click "Request More" to receive a batch of anonymized cases derived from your hospital's dataset.

- 3 **Start Annotation** – After being assigned the data, click the blue button labelled "x Assigned to You" to begin labelling, where x will be the number of data assigned to you.

5. V7 Annotation Interface Basics

After clicking on the blue button (Table 2 – step 3), you will be redirected to the **annotation interface** (Figure 7.). This screen is divided into four main sections, each designed to streamline the annotation process. Below is a brief overview of these sections, including how to navigate and interact with them to **ensure accurate data labelling for AI model development**.

1. Main Canvas (Video/Image Display Area)

The Main Canvas is the central workspace where medical images or video frames appear. You will interact with the dataset here by placing, adjusting, and reviewing annotations.

2. Annotation Tools Sidebar

Located on the left side of the screen, the Annotation Tools Sidebar provides various annotation tools for labelling data, but for our purposes the one you need to use is the polygon tool.

3. Active Annotations Sidebar

Located on the right side of the interface, the Active Annotations Sidebar serves two primary functions. The top section allows you to manage and organize the labels assigned to the current video frame or image. Below, in the Tags section, you will find all available annotation tags. However, for this process, only the ACEP Grading Score tag should be selected.

4. Bottom Bar (Navigation & Playback)

The Bottom Bar has two key functions: selecting the clip or image for labelling and, for video clips, navigating through individual frames.

Figure 7. The annotation interface in V7 labs. 1) the main canvas showing the anonymized DICOM file, 2) sidebar with the various annotation tools, 3) sidebar with the active annotations and 4) navigation and playback bar.

6. Step-by-Step DICOM Video Labelling Procedure on V7

The following guide outlines the step-by-step process for **labelling key frames** in a **DICOM clip** on V7 Table 3. Steps to be followed for a DICOM file annotation.. This process should be repeated for each key frame specified in **Section 2: Labelling Instructions**, which includes:

- Non-compressed/Neutral Phase (1 frame).
- Mid-Compression Phase (2-3 frames).
- Peak-Compression Phase (1 frame).
- Artery Deformation (1-2 frames).

Table 3. Steps to be followed for a DICOM file annotation.

Step 1. Setup the default annotation settings

Navigate to the **Bottom Bar (navigation & Playback)** and follow these steps:

- a) Click on the 3 dots in the top right corner (1) and a pop-up with settings will appear.

- b) Set the "Default annotation length" (2) setting value to 1 by either clicking on the "-" symbol or by clicking on the value area and entering the number 1 from your keyboard.

- c) Click on the Zoom out button (3) until the timeline expands enough so that you can see all the available frames of the clip.
- d) Finally click anywhere on the screen for the setting to save the settings.

Step 2. Select the correct frame

Use the timeline section in the **Bottom Bar (Navigation & Playback)** to find the correct frames (start by locating the non-compressed/neutral phase frame):

- a) Click on the desired frame in the timeline.
- b) Alternatively, use the "<" and ">" keyboard shortcuts to navigate through the frames.
- c) You can also play the clip by clicking on the play button or hitting the spacebar key on your keyboard.
- d) **Disregard the first four frames and begin labelling from the fifth frame onward.**

Step 3. Review clip information

In the **Bottom Bar (Navigation & Playback)**, hover over the clip icon to review the relevant clip details from the standardized filename, including:

- a) **Scanning Location** — In this case, the scanning location is labelled as "1", based on the CFV tag*.
- b) **Left or right leg** — In this case, the clip is from the right leg, based on the capital "R" tag
- c) **Adequate or inadequate data** — In this case, the quality of the clip is adequate, based on the absence of the lowercase "r"

- CFV tag -> Scanning Location 1
- GSV tag -> Scanning Location 2
- FV tag -> Scanning Location 3
- PV tag -> Scanning Location 4

Step 4. Apply the ACEP grading score

In the **Active Annotations Sidebar (3)** (top right corner), review the relevant clip details, including scanning location, leg side (right or left), and whether the data is adequate or inadequate.

- a) Navigate to the **Active Annotations Sidebar (3)** (bottom right corner), locate the ACEP Grading Score under the Tags section.

- b) Select it, and it will move to the top right of the sidebar.

- c) Click on it to assign the appropriate ACEP Grading Score based on the reference ACEP table in this document.
- d) This score applies only to the specific frame.
- e) If the assigned ACEP Grading Score is 2 or above, proceed with **step 5** (segmentation/tracing of vessels)

Step 5. Apply the segmentation mask

In the **Active Annotations Sidebar (3)** (top right corner), review the relevant clip details, including scanning location, leg side (right or left), and whether the data is adequate or inadequate.

- a) Navigate to the **Annotation Tools Sidebar (2)** (top left corner), select the polygon tool
- b) A dropdown menu will appear containing all available segmentation classes which are a combination of anatomical structure and scanning location.
- c) Based on the clip details from Step 3, select the appropriate segmentation class for the specific frame.

- d) Move your cursor to the **Main Canvas (1)** and begin annotating according to the Section 2: Labelling Instructions mentioned previously in the document.
- e) Use the left mouse click to place points along the vessel borders.
- f) Ensure the segmentation mask forms a closed loop by connecting the last point to the first.
- g) The segmentation mask will appear in both the **Main Canvas (1)** and the **Active Annotations Sidebar (3)**

Step 6. Navigate to the next frame

Use the timeline section in the **Bottom Bar (Navigation & Playback)** to proceed to the next key frame that needs to be annotated according to the **Section 2: Labelling Instructions**.

- a) Click on the desired frame in the timeline.
- b) Alternatively, use the "<" and ">" keyboard shortcuts to navigate through the frames.
- c) You can also play the clip by clicking on the play button or hitting the spacebar key on your keyboard.

- d) Click on the desired frame in the timeline.

Step 7. Repeat for all frames

Repeat **Steps 1–6** until all required frames in the clip are labelled.

Step 8. Complete the annotation process for the clip

Once you have completed annotating all the key frames for the DICOM clip (5-7 frames in total), click on the **Mark as Complete** button (top right corner). This will change the status of this DICOM clip to completed and the next DICOM clip or image for labelling will appear on your screen.

7. Reference DICOM Clip Annotated

Below is a reference DICOM video containing all the annotations for a normal patient (**CFV Scanning Location 1, CFA Scanning Location 1, ACEP Grading Score**) (Table 4. A reference DICOM video from the Common Femoral Vein annotated (Right leg).) on each of the following frames according to **the Section 2: Labelling Instructions:**

- Non-compressed/Neutral Phase (1 frame)
- Mid-Compression Phase (3 frames)
- Peak-Compression Phase (1 frame)
- Artery Deformation (2 frames)

Table 4. A reference DICOM video from the Common Femoral Vein annotated (Right leg).

Annotation description **Reference image**

Annotation 1: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is in the neutral phase (not compressed).

Annotation 2: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is partially compressed.

Annotation 3: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is partially compressed.

Annotation 4: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is partially compressed.

Annotation 5: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is fully compressed.

Annotation 6: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is fully compressed, and artery is deformed.

Annotation 7: Common Femoral Vein (CFV – blue) and Common Femoral Artery (CFA – red) annotated in a frame where vein is fully compressed, and artery is deformed.

8. Common V7 Labelling Issues & Best Practices

1. Excessive Number of Annotation Points

- **Issue:**
 - Over-annotating vascular structures by adding too many points.
- **Impact:**
 - Introduces spikes and irregularities in the shape contour.
 - Complicates segmentation mask adjustments.
 - Slows down the labelling workflow due to unnecessary complexity.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Use only the minimum number of points necessary to trace the anatomical structure accurately.

2. Insufficient Number of Annotation Points

- **Issue:**
 - Using an insufficient number of annotation points to trace anatomical structures.
- **Impact:**
 - Leads to poor geometric approximation of the true anatomical structure.

- Reduces model performance due to inadequate training data.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Ensure sufficient points are added to preserve anatomical fidelity.

3. Incorrect Annotation Propagation

- **Issue:**
 - Annotations are unintentionally extended across multiple frames (30 by default).
- **Impact:**
 - Annotations are replicated across unintended frames (29 extra).
 - This introduces significant errors.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Set the annotation length to 1 frame to restrict it to the intended frame only.

Labels if default annotation length = 30 (Incorrect):

Labels if default annotation length = 1 (Correct):

4. Missing ACEP Grading

- **Issue:**
 - Omission of the ACEP Grading score in annotated frames.
- **Impact:**
 - Results in incomplete metadata.
 - Reduces the labelled dataset's utility for AI model training.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Always assign an ACEP Grading score, even for random or inadequate frames.

5. Missing Segmentation Masks in Random/Inadequate Frames

- **Issue:**
 - Segmentation masks are sometimes skipped in frames marked as inadequate with an ACEP grading score ≥ 2 .
- **Impact:**
 - Results in missed opportunities to train the model on visible structures, even in low-quality frames.
 - Limits the diversity of training data.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Include segmentation masks for all frames with any recognizable structures (ACEP Grading Score ≥ 2)

6. Labelling Inconsistencies

- **Issue:**
 - Segmentation masks are occasionally applied to frames marked as ACEP Grading 1 (no recognizable structures).
- **Impact:**
 - Degrades overall data integrity.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Ensure alignment between ACEP Grading and segmentation presence. **Do not add masks to frames graded 1**, where by definition no recognizable structures exist (ACEP grading score 1 = No recognizable structures, no objective data can be gathered).

7. Use of Wrong Segmentation Mask

- **Issue:**
 - Used the wrong anatomical structure and/or scanning location. Each segmentation mask includes both the vascular structure and its corresponding scanning location (Scanning Location 1 to 4).
- **Impact:**
 - Creates inconsistency in dataset labelling standards and can lead to deteriorated model performance.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Select the correct segmentation mask by verifying both the vascular structure and scanning location before finalizing annotations. Refer to the standardized labelling guidelines for each location.

8. Duplicate ACEP Grading on the Same Frame

- **Issue:**
 - ACEP grading applied more than once on a single frame, sometimes repeating the same grade or applying different ones.

- **Impact:**
 - Creates ambiguity and inconsistency in grading labels.
 - Can lead to conflicts in automated evaluation systems.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Ensure only one ACEP grading score is applied per frame. Review before submitting to avoid duplicates.

9. Segmentation Masks Extending Outside the Ultrasound Area

- **Issue:**
 - Segmentation masks drawn beyond the visible ultrasound region in the main canvas.
- **Impact:**
 - Decreases the accuracy of the labelled region.
 - May cause errors in downstream label processing.
- **Recommendation:**
 - Apply all segmentation masks strictly within the ultrasound-visible area.

